

WAYS TO USE SPECIAL RUNNING EXERCISES TO MASTER LOW START TECHNIQUES

Daminov Ilkhomjon Ashiralievich

Professor at Termez State Pedagogical Institute

Ashiraliev Bobur Ilkhom ougli

Teacher at the military-academic lyceum “Yosh chegarachilar”

Termez city, Republic of Uzbekistan

Annotation: This article is devoted to the study of special running exercises and their role in mastering the low start technique in runners. The importance of the low start technique in achieving high sports results and methods for improving it through specialized exercises are considered. The article presents the results of a study demonstrating the effectiveness of using special running exercises to improve starting skills, increase acceleration speed and reduce the risk of injury.

Key words: running exercises, low start technique, specialized training, sports results, acceleration speed, coordination of movements, injuries, improving starting skills, training effectiveness.

Introduction. Nowadays, low start technique plays an important role in achieving success in running disciplines. Regardless of the athlete’s level of training, proper mastery and improvement of this technique has a significant impact on his athletic performance. In this regard, the relevance of the article “Methods of using special running exercises to master the low start technique” is undeniable for the following reasons [1]:

Improved Performance: Mastering the low launch technique allows athletes to achieve higher launch speeds, which is critical in running competitions [2, 3].

Injury prevention: Proper execution of a running start reduces the risk of injuries, especially those associated with improper distribution of load on muscles and joints [5].

Improving technique: Mastering the low-start technique helps develop good running habits, which can subsequently improve overall running technique and performance at various distances [4].

In light of the prospects for further development of running disciplines and the constant desire of athletes to improve their performance, this article on ways to use specific running exercises to master low-start techniques is an important resource for coaches, athletes and anyone interested in the development of running sports.

The purpose of this article is to study and systematize special running exercises that contribute to the development of low start techniques. It is aimed at providing coaches and athletes with specific methods and recommendations for using such exercises to improve the efficiency of starts in running disciplines.

Improving Launch Performance: Specific running drills help athletes improve their low launch technique, which allows for faster, more efficient acceleration at the start of a race. This allows athletes to achieve better results in competitions and increases their competitiveness.

Mastering special exercises helps improve coordination and control of movements, which makes the start more stable and reliable. This allows athletes to more consistently achieve optimal acceleration at the start and avoid mistakes. Proper execution of specific exercises helps develop strength, flexibility and balance, which reduces the risk of injury during the start. This is especially important for athletes involved in running disciplines, where the correct start plays a decisive role.

I offer a variety of specific exercises that can be tailored to the individual needs and fitness level of the athletes. This allows coaches to create individualized training programs that take into account the characteristics of each athlete. Special running exercises are designed to train and improve low start skills. Among them are:

Application of special running exercises	
Running from a high start	Repeated starting with minimal time between attempts to develop reaction speed and improve coordination of movements.
Running from a low start over short distances	Start training for short distances, which helps to focus on technique and develop pushing power.
Acceleration exercises	Running exercises that focus on acceleration and speed development, such as high-speed intervals or tail runs, help improve launch dynamics.
Exercises to develop technique	Particular attention is paid to the technical aspects of the start, such as body position, weight distribution, and arm and leg function.

Incorporating specific running exercises into a daily training program allows athletes to systematically work on improving their low-start technique. The practice of these exercises is necessary for the formation of automated movements and confidence in the execution of starts in competitive conditions.

The study examined various ways to use special running exercises to master the low start technique. Training sessions were held with the participation of runners of various levels of training, including special exercises aimed at improving starting skills. The following results were obtained during the study:

Improving the technical execution of the start: Conducting special running exercises led to a noticeable improvement in the low start technique of the study

participants. They began to perform the start more confidently and coordinatedly, which was reflected in the quality of their acceleration over the distance.

Increasing launch speed: Specialized training allowed study participants to improve launch dynamics and increase acceleration speed in the first meters of the distance. This had a positive effect on the overall finishing time in the running trials.

Reduced risk of errors: Regular practice of specific exercises helped automate the correct movements when starting and reduced the likelihood of technical errors in competitive conditions.

The results obtained confirm the effectiveness of using special running exercises to master the low start technique. Improving technical performance and increasing start speed are important factors determining the success of performance in running disciplines. In addition, reducing the risk of starting errors reduces the likelihood of negative consequences and increases the athletes' confidence in their abilities.

These results confirm the importance of including specific running exercises in the training process of runners at all levels of training. Further research could be aimed at exploring the optimal training methods and programs to maximize the effect of using specific exercises in different conditions and among different groups of athletes.

In modern running, low start technique plays a key role in achieving high athletic results. Using specific running drills to master this technique is an effective approach that helps improve starting skills and proficiency in runners at any skill level.

The results of the study showed that regular specialized training using special exercises leads to improved technical execution of the start, increased acceleration speed and reduced risk of errors. These factors play an important role in achieving success in running disciplines and improving the performance of athletes.

Conclusions. Thus, the use of special running exercises to master the low start technique is an integral part of the training process for runners. This approach not

only helps improve your performance in competition, but also develops the coordination, strength and speed needed to perform successfully on the course.

References:

1. Ильина, И. А. (2013). Рациональное использование специальных беговых упражнений на занятиях по легкой атлетике. *Вестник Ленинградского государственного университета им. АС Пушкина*, 3(4), 116-122.
2. Фадеев, А. С., Пронин, Е. А., Горобец, В. И., Евсиков, С. А., Ивченко, В. В., & Барлит, В. В. (2023). Основы тренировки бега на короткие дистанции в лёгкой атлетике. *Ученые записки университета им. ПФ Лесгафта*, (3 (217)), 483-487.
3. Daminov, I. A. (2023). Kurash musobaqalari va o'qitish metodikasi. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*, 2(2), 150-157.
4. Салимов, У. Ш. (2023). Факультативный предмет " нетрадиционные методы здорового образа жизни" как средство совершенствования физической активности студентов. *Fan-Sportga*, (1), 83-85.
5. Alimov, T., & Abduraimov, S. (2023). Yosh futbolchilarning mashg'ulotlariga qo'yiladigan talablar. *Interpretation and researches*, 2(1).